

People Participation as Social Capital Form for Realizing Sustainable Ecotourism

Authors : I. Putu Eka N. Kencana, I. Wayan Mertha

Abstract : A variety of research's evidence suggests that community involvement is one of the vital elements in the development of sustainable tourism. As an entity of the tourism system, local communities are considered have better understanding of their region as well as influenced positively or negatively by the tourism activities in the region. This study elaborates role of community involvement in the development of ecotourism in Kintamani Bali from two perspectives of view, namely participation in the process of initiatives development and participation in the economic benefits of tourism. As one element of social capital form, community participation on the development and management of ecotourism in Kintamani, could be expected maintain its sustainability.

Keywords : community involvement, ecotourism, participation, social capital

Conference Title : ICSTM 2014 : International Conference on Sustainable Tourism Management

Conference Location : Bali, Indonesia

Conference Dates : October 09-10, 2014